

GRAPHIC SKILLS AND ORGANIZATIONAL-METHODICAL CONDITIONS OF ITS FORMATION

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Abstract: The article describes graphic skills and organizational-methodical conditions of its formation, specific features and methods of teaching writing techniques. The stages of teaching graphic skills and the organizational-methodical conditions of its formation are shown.

Key words: graphic skills, frontal work, functional, classroom board, hygienic requirement, pedagogical requirement, one-seat desk, two-seat desk, distance, positive distance, negative distance.

Reasonable ideas on reforming and re-providing primary education were put forward by our head of state. After that, a number of laws, decisions and instructions were announced, and the implementation of them was widespread in the educational institutions of our republic. At the moment, certain measures have been planned and certain works have been carried out in this regard, but there are still many urgent issues that need to be resolved.

Our observations show that the age and physical fitness of elementary school students, especially in the first grade, play a big role in their literacy. For example, at the first stages of the formation of writing and reading skills, the child uses all his strength - physical and mental capabilities - to perform writing and reading exercises: during the writing process, all the muscles of the student, especially the muscles of the arms and shoulders, back and Leg veins and nerves become more tense. Therefore, teachers carefully monitor this process, take into account the speed of movement of finger and hand muscles, correct sitting at the desk, physical and mental condition and readiness of students.

Naturally, the processes of writing and reading take place under physical and mental stress in the initial stages. The child digests the first problem and failure with difficulty. Therefore, physical and mental stress will not give the expected effect. The student notices and understands his mistake, but cannot eliminate it even with the guidance of his student. In such cases, the teacher plays a variety of exciting games to raise the student's morale and mood. Such momentary physical and mental breaks moderate the child's mental stress and increase the child's mastery and acceptance of the subject. What we have said

will bear fruit at that time, that for the education of a primary school student, especially a first grade student, both organizational and methodical work should be prepared at an excellent level. What is included in organizational and methodical work? Let's debate it!

Creating a developing environment is of great importance for the formation of graphic skills of first graders. First of all, the developing environment helps to organize the workplace of students in a methodically correct, error-free and efficient manner. In this environment, a first-grader feels more relaxed and confident.

How to solve the problem of placing students in the workplace, especially in the classroom, in a developing environment. In this regard, a lot of work has been done in Russian schools and new ideas are being implemented. We will respond to some of them.

School classes are usually similar and adapted only for frontal work. There is a blackboard in front, the teacher's place next to it, desks in front of it. But this arrangement is not very convenient for blended learning or group work in the classroom.

It is not necessary to buy equipment and expensive repairs to make the lessons in the classroom interesting, modern and at the same time to facilitate the work of the teacher in the classroom. Sometimes it is enough for a teacher to know the basic methods of classroom management, how to use the available resources and zoning the space for different forms of educational activities. This approach is called classroom design. We will tell you which zones in the classroom will be the most comfortable and functional.

A student spends most of his time in the classroom with the following educational tools: desk, blackboard, notebook, pen, etc. Therefore, it is of great importance that educational tools meet hygienic and pedagogical requirements. As we mentioned, schoolchildren spend a lot of time sitting at their desks. Therefore, during this responsible period, students should be taught to follow the hygienic requirements.

It is important to equip classrooms with desks that meet hygiene requirements in order to ensure that work ability does not decrease for a long time, and to ensure the proper development of children's stature, to ensure that the eyes are not negatively affected during the study period, and to form the graphic skills of students. First of all, the teacher must create the necessary conditions for his student's moderate work. Preparation for this job starts in August. The teacher should check whether the classroom and the desks in it are

suitable for the work of his future students. After accepting his students to school, he used to assign them to desks according to their height, sight and hearing abilities.

First of all, classroom desks should fully meet pedagogical requirements. These requirements are:

1. Appropriateness to the age and height of students.
2. It should fit the body of the students.
3. It should be convenient for writing and drawing.
4. It should not be difficult for the student to stand or sit.

In the first desk on the window side, students with low vision or low hearing should be seated. There should be three rows of desks in the classroom. The distance between the first desk and the blackboard should not be less than 2 meters, and the distance between the last desk and the blackboard should not be less than 8 meters. This distance is necessary for children to see and hear the teacher well. The distance between the window and the last board inside should not exceed 6 meters.

The distance between the boards between the rows should be 75 cm. This distance is necessary for two students to move freely between the rows.

Our observations and experiences testify that in the primary classes of many general education schools, these requirements are not observed at all, or they are grossly violated. Firstly, the students' desks are not suitable for their age, height and body. In fact, desks can be single or double. Single-seater desks are often used in foreign countries.

Two-seater desks are currently being used in the schools of our republic. It should be noted that the two-seater wooden desks created by Professor F. F. Erisman were very convenient from the hygienic point of view.

But unfortunately, at the moment, such desks are completely out of use.

According to the requirement, the slope of the desk should be equal to 15° , because it is very comfortable to write and read at such a slope, and the eyes do not tire quickly (Fig. 1).

Figure 1

Another important requirement is that the lid of the desk can be opened and closed. If the desk does not have a cover that can be opened and closed, it will be inconvenient for the student to get up and sit down. As a result, this discomfort can have a negative effect on the child's psyche. It is a pity that there is no such cover on the desks in use now. The stability of the desk chair is the most important factor in ensuring proper sitting. It is even better if the seat board is slightly inclined towards the back. For students to sit more comfortably, the height of the backrest should be higher than the student's waist.

There is a concept called desk distance. The distance is the distance between the lower edge of the table top and the backrest. This distance, that is, the distance between the chest and its edge, should be 4 cm. At the moment, desks with a flat top, separate seats, different heights and structures (iron and wooden desks, desks) without footrests are used in primary classes of many schools. Gross violations of such hygienic and pedagogical requirements have an irreparable negative impact on the quality of education. Imagine a first grader sitting at an office desk with a low chair and writing instead of a desk. Because the chair is low, he raises his arms and tries to sit comfortably on the desk, but soon both arms start to hurt. As a result, he loses focus and becomes restless. In

the process of writing, he starts to make mistakes, and naturally, he also gets nervous. In order to avoid such situations, the distance of the desk should be kept correctly.

According to the requirement, the distance of the desk can be of three types: positive, zero, negative. In positive distance, the distance between the edge of the desk and the seat is equal. The line drawn from the edge of the tabletop falls on the floor, not on the chair (Fig. 2).

Figure 3

Sitting at the desks shown in the picture above will be uncomfortable for students. When the student sits at such desks, he is forced to sit down.

At zero distance, there is no distance between the edge of the desk and the seat. A line drawn from the edge of the tabletop will match the edge of the seat (Figure 3). Such desks will not be comfortable for students.

Figure 3

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